

Article

Voter's Perception of Political Messages Against the Elite Classes in Spain: A Quasi-Experimental Design

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Abstract

Demonization constitutes the construction of a simplified symbolic reality through the prism of hatred. The elite classes have been framed within the discourse of far-left parties in Spain to make them antagonistic to their target audience. In this area, research tends to use explicit measures, but few have used implicit measures. This article aims to assess both types of voter perceptions of anti-elite class messages in Spain. Eighty Spanish voters belonging to left- and right-wing ideologies participated in this study. Implicit attitudes were measured through the implicit association test. The result shows that demonization is deepening in various layers of society in order to provoke a confrontation with the elite classes. Social networks have emerged as a means of social control, but they are not perceived as such by the subjects but rather as an additional informational or purely propagandistic element. But even among the public who are aware of the latter, the more their perception of the elite classes is limited to demonization, the more extreme their social vision is.

Keywords

demonization; elite classes; hate speech; polarization; political discourse; social networks

Issue

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1. Introduction

The current development of technologies, as well as their potential, provides great advances and benefits that cannot be ignored in almost any field, including the media (Tuesta-Panduro, 2021). However, the media has been expanding and continues to expand its contact channels to provide information and, especially within the framework of web 2.0, this has led to harmful effects such as the creation and subsequent viralization of fake news and the emergence of hate messages (Rani et al., 2022). Such pernicious information is created by combining typographic and visual elements that accentuate the manipulative intention (Rodríguez Ferrándiz & Sorolla-Romero, 2021).

However, disinformation is not only framed from the point of view of the media; it extends to other areas such as corporate communication, institutional communication, and political communication (Mut Camacho & Rueda Lozano, 2021). What sets a common pattern in all the aforementioned areas is the possibility of building communicative strategies that favor disinformation, boost hate speech, and contribute to the polarization of public opinion (Gidron et al., 2020; López del Castillo Wilderbeek, 2021). Thus, new ecosystems of information manipulation are generated where society is unaware of reality and fixes the framework through pernicious messages (Larrondo-Ureta et al., 2021).

When polarization occurs, the center of the board is usually emptied, and a great deal of stress is put on

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